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The Impact of Nerfund on Small and Medium Enterprises

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Abstract

The research focused on the impact of NERFUND on small and medium enterprises in Jos Metropolis. The objectives of this work are; to appraise financial challenges of small and medium scale enterprises, to appraise the effectiveness of various SME agencies set up by the federal government to promote activities of SMEs and to examine the impact of NERFUND on small and medium scale enterprises in Jos South Local Government. The research design of this study is a survey design; the survey design was adopted due to its scientific and philosophical assumption which guarantees the application of sampling and generalization of the research findings. The target population of the study is 100 and the sample size using the Taro Yamane formula was 50. Secondary data was used to develop the literature review and primary data was use to collect the data which was presented and analyze using simple percentage method. The findings of this work are; accessing intervention fund requires legal mortgage whereby so many SMEs do not have the requirement to loan, there was internal bank guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtain loan and there is effective research and development output among SMEs owners. The recommendations of the study by the researcher were; risk can be reduced in small scale enterprises if the central bank of Nigeria and the government can do more than they are currently doing, in order to make credit available to small scale enterprises, the government and the public should introduce the use of rural banking programme, the government should combine savings scheme for small scales industrial sector with their credit programme such as a scheme would provide further means of financing the government and create attachment of the industrialist to the government and also solve the problem of very short moratorium period granted by government to small scale enterprises.

Keywords: Nerfund, Small and Medium Enterprises

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The promotion and development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) through effective financing options has generated a lot of debates among researchers, policymakers, and entrepreneurs because of its immense cultivation to the economic growth of any country in the world (Akingunola, 2019). Government financing helps SMEs to improve both immediate and future performance as measured by income, growth, and survival or profitability as well as non-financial performance in terms of the level of satisfaction. This could be because government financial assistance quickly overcomes the financial constraints endemic in SMEs. Government financial assistance also helps SMEs obtain nongovernment finance in the future (Dong & Andrew, 2017).

According to Ouguiya (2014), since independence, promoting small and medium scale enterprises as the foundation of economic progress has been recognized in Nigeria by every regime (SME, 2015). This is because of its perceived relevance in ensuring sustained increase in per-capita income and output, as well as, employment generation and promotion of effective utilization of available resource (s).

Small Scale Enterprises (SSEs) have attracted considerable attention of both public and private sectors in more than two decades ago chiefly in most of the less developed nations. In a considerable number of such

countries, government makes provisions for policies that are deemed promoting in their development plans, policies and programmes for the promotion of small scale enterprises because of their perceived benefit to economic development. For instance, these perceived ideal benefits include: employment generation especially for people in rural areas, transformation of traditional to modern technology, stimulation of indigenous entrepreneurship, reversal of urban-rural migration, greater utilization of raw materials, promotion of local technology, mobilization of local savings, linkage balance by spreading investment more evenly, ability to operate profitably in very narrow markets with low purchasing power, among others. The extent of resources allocated to each sector varies considerably from country to Country. Previously, incentives were provided to favour large-scale enterprises, small scale enterprises were usually relegated to the background (FMST, 2019).

Driven by these, several financial institutions in charge of microcredit and policy instruments such as Nigeria Agricultural Co-operative and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB), Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND), Bank of Industry (BI) among others were established to facilitate growth of small scale enterprises. And of recent Small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS), Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency (SMEDA) and other policy oriented institutions like Entrepreneurship Development Policy (EDP) run by the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Industrial Development Centres (IDC) among others were introduced to offer technical and financial assistance to small scale enterprises.

In spite of these interventions undertaken by successive governments to improve the performance of small scale enterprises, judging by SME performance, not much progress seems to have been achieved, This study examines survey data in order to evaluate the relevance of government interventions on SMEs; their effectiveness and the sensitization of the small scale enterprises operators on their existence and importance and to determine why these interventions may not have achieved their goals in relation to the growth performance of small scale enterprise in Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Several studies have identified financial constraint as the major obstacle to Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development in developing countries including Nigeria. For instance, Adelaja (2010) argued that the access to institutional finance has always constituted a pandemic problem for SME development in Nigeria. He recalled that in the past, a number of schemes have been put in place to provide special credit lines/ windows for SMEs but this achieved very limited impact.

The primary focus of this study emanates from the fact that small scale enterprises owners do not have sufficient finance to carry on their due to the low saving culture of the people in this part of the world. The reason for this is not far fetch: low level of income basically. While it is an established fact that Small and Medium Scale Enterprises face financial challenges, no research has been conducted to investigate the effect the financial problem on their contribution to economic development.

Asaolu (2018) and many other authors and researchers have deduced that the financial challenges mar the developmental role of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises. But this may not be true especially in the case of Nigeria where the informal sector, which is constituted largely by the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises play a very important role in the development of the nation's economy. Therefore, this study seeks to evaluate the impact of NERFUND in the promotion and development of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to critically examine the impact of NERFUND on the promotion and development of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Jos South Local Government.

Specific objectives of the study are:

1. To identify the government funding programme on some selected SMEs in Jos.
2. To identify the perception of industrialization on the development of some selected SMEs in Jos.
3. To determine the impact of financial expertise on the development of some selected SMEs in Jos.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In-order to achieve the objectives of the study, the following research questions will guide the study:

1. What financial challenges are faced by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Jos South Local Government?
2. How effective are various SME agencies set up by the federal government to promote activities of SMEs in Jos South Local Government?
3. What impact NERFUND has on Small and medium scale enterprises in Jos South Local Government?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

It is expected that at the end of this study the result to be obtained will be of immense benefit to the organization captured as the case study in its policies formulation and implementation, the result will also be very crucial in adding to the existing knowledge. In fact, the researcher himself will find the outcome of the study of great importance because it will expose him to series of ideas and knowledge which will help him in future as a manager.

The research will also serve as criteria for the award of National Diploma to the researcher.

SCOPE AND DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This research work focuses on the impact of NERFUND on the promotion and development of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria paying special attention to the impact the government of Nigeria has on the development of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises through the establishment of NERFUND.

The research intends to study the essential problems encountered by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises and suggest ways by which they can be adequately and efficiently financed.

Most of the information and data needed for the study would be gathered from existing literature and from relevant government agencies such as the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) etc.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Various bodies/organization defined SMEs in their own perspective depending on the purpose, objective and use.

In the context and purpose of this research, the following definitions were adopted:

NERFUND: This is a government parastatals / Agency which make funds available in the form of grant, credit facilities to the industrialist or entrepreneurs.

Small Scale Enterprise: This is an industry with a labour size of between 11-100 workers or a total cost including working capital but excluding cost of land) not more than fifty million naira only (N50m) and/or a turnover of less than ten million naira only (N10m)

Medium Scale Enterprise: This is an industry with a labour size of 101 – 300 workers or a total cost including working capital but excluding cost of land) of over fifty million naira only (N50m) but not more than two hundred million naira only (N200m).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept Of NERFUND

Sequel to the introduction of structural Adjustment programme (SAP) in 1986 and the subsequent devaluation of currency, coupled with sharp rise in interest rate, many small and medium scale Enterprises found it difficult to obtain loan to finance their investment. To bridge the gap, the federal government in 1990 set up the National

Economic Reconstruction Fund to provide relatively long-term loans (5-10 years) to small and medium scale Enterprises at a very low interest rate.

The aims and objectives of the Fund are: to correct any observed inadequacies in the provision of medium to long term financing to small and medium scale industrial enterprises, especially manufacturing and agro-allied enterprises and ancillary services. It is also required to provide medium to long term loans to participating commercial and merchant banks for on-lending to small and medium scale enterprises for the promotion and acceleration of productive activities in such enterprises.

In addition it facilitates the provision of loans with five to ten year maturity, including a grace period of one to three years, depending on the nature of the enterprises or project. It is also mandated to provide such loans either in naira or in foreign currencies or both according the source of funds available to the Fund and the requirements of the eligible enterprises or project.

NERFUND operations have had far reaching impact on the Nigerian economy. Apart from helping to conscientize Nigerians in the early '90s to embark on manufacturing rather than merchandize foreign made goods, the fund has helped to create jobs for teeming Nigerians and contributed immensely to GDP. Take the 266 projects disbursed between 1990 and 1998, they estimated to generate about 18,620 direct and 148,000 indirect employments to Nigerians, Current disbursements are on- going but the 721 micro enterprises so far approved are capable of creating about 3,605 direct jobs.

The definitions ascribed to SMEs vary across countries and institutions. Most definitions advanced are based on quantitative factors such as number of workers, assets and sales, sometimes differentiated by industrial sector. In the opinion of Kushnir, Mirmulstein & Ramalho business culture, size of the country's population, industry, level of international economic integration and even political reasons also play a role for governments to decide on a certain definition. Bartlett asserted that new definitions should be industry-specific and Gibson & Van der Vaart suggested that "single definitions of SMEs for multiple countries in diverse stages of development" contribute to distortions in the allocation of resources for private sector development.

Whereas Gibson & Van der Vaart argued an adjusted measure of the volume of turnover in relation to the per-capita gross national income at purchasing parity as a more appropriate measure. Also, the review of extant literature on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) indicates that the definition of SMEs differs across countries, which is based on factors such as the country 's level of business activities and economic development, the size of SMEs and especially the challenges experienced by SMEs.

Therefore, this suggest there is no universally accepted definition of SMEs However, In Nigeria, factors such as asset base (excluding land), the number of employees and the annual turnover are used to classify these SMEs. Hence, according to Federal Ministry of Industries, a small-scale enterprise is one whose total assets are less than N50 million, with less than 100 employees. Annual turnover is not considered in the definition of an SME. Small and Medium Enterprises as defined by the National Council of Industries in Nigeria refers to business enterprises whose total costs; excluding land, is not more than two hundred million naira (N200,000,000.00) only.

SMEs are regarded as facilitator to the socio-economic growth and development of every country economy, and serves as absolute instrument and engine for the accomplishment of macroeconomic objectives of employment creation at little investment cost and enhancement of entrepreneurial capabilities, reducing rural-urban migration, promoting indigenous technology, utilization of local resources and poverty alleviation (Asikhia, 2010). Small businesses are accredited as the seedbed of industrial development. In Nigeria, SMEs besides their employment and income creation for the larger proportion of the county's citizens, it is also acknowledge as the medium for indigenous entrepreneurial capabilities, industrial innovativeness, practical skills and organizational skills for business sector development (Abdullahi, Tahir, Aliyu and Abubakar, 2015). According to Begum and Abdin (2015), the private sector which mainly comprise of micro, small and medium enterprises have the capacity to generate larger share of employment and income opportunities. For example, in Bangladesh, there

are about 177 SMEs clusters having 19, 37,809 employees and workers and for which 14, 33,979 and 5, 03,830 constitutes number of male and female respectively. Though substantial number of jobs created by SMEs constitutes low paying, but makes possible for families to survive, educate their kids and in some instances move out of poverty (Lawal, Ajonbadi & Otokiti, 2014). SMEs provide rural employment opportunities particularly to the unskilled labour force and thus increases living standard of the rural poor (Vijayakumar, 2013). SMEs makes women who are more vulnerable to poverty to be self-employed, it serve as an umbrella for displaced workers from formal employment and also the disabilities (Munoz, Welsh, Chan & Raven, 2015).

Also, SMEs provide an important ground for creation and development of indigenous entrepreneurs in many aspects of economic activity. Some successful Nigeria entrepreneurs for example, Folawiyo, Okoya's Eleganza, dantata, Dangote and Bank Anthony started their entrepreneurship career as small business owners (Lawal, Ajonbadi & Otokiti, 2014; Darwish, 2014).

Functions of National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND)

The challenge for those who seek to benefit from the program is to come up with a viable project that will entice the panelists and they will dance home as beneficiaries; no politicking.

So far, the NERFUND has recorded a great percentage of success in re-orienting the economy of the nation towards a culture of production from the outdated culture. Since its inception, the NERFUND has approved and disbursed loans up to one thousand four hundred and ninety-seven (1497) projects with a total estimation of five billion Naira (5,000,000,000,000).

The vision of the Organization hence is to establish a world-class Development Finance Institution (DFI) which will be built around transparency, quality service delivery, professionalism, and integrity.

In order to achieve their vision, they support and encourage the growth of the domestic Micro, Small, and Medium Scale industrial enterprises by providing a means through which they can get long-term financing.

Aside from just the disbursement of loans, other functions of the NERFUND includes:

1. They take up a measure to effect correction upon any inadequacies in providing financing on a long-term basis to small and medium scale enterprises especially when it has to do with manufacturing and agro-allied ancillary services and enterprises.
2. Make provision for loans on a small to long-term basis to commercial and merchant banks that participate in the program for lending to small and medium scale businesses in order to promote and speed up production activities in such companies.
3. Ensure and speed up the process of loan disbursement with a lifespan of five to ten years and occasionally, with a grace period of one to three years still dependent upon the nature of the business for which the loan was gotten for.
4. Give out loans either in local or foreign currencies or in some cases, in both depending on the sources from which the fund came from and the requirement of the company that is eligible for the loan.

Types of NERFUND Loans

The Micro Credit Scheme was recently started to cater for low-budget business owners who are the vast majority and are focused mostly on micro scale. This introduction became necessary because commercial and industry banks are not too keen to provide credit to this sector of the business community. The main objective of this scheme is poverty alleviation and increases the GDP growth rate.

The target audiences are graduates, women societies, market associations, artisans and lots more who are engaged in cottage industries, and small scale manufacturing/food processing, etc. This fund is valued below Five Million Naira (N5, 000,000.00). Other attributes of this product include, but not limited to the following:

- Collateral Free Single
- Digit interest rate (8%)
- 3 – 6 months moratorium period

- Three years tenor period One percent appraisal fee (one-off payment)
- 10% equity contribution.

Importance of NERFUND to SMEs

Out of the arising need to provide the needed means of financing small and medium scale businesses on a long term basis that the National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) was established in 1989 as a product of the NERFUND Act, cap.254, 1990 Laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

The National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) was established to boost the production scale of SMEs. The major importance of the NERFUND is that it helps in boosting up the number of services and goods that are produced through its program and made available for consumption locally as well as for exportation and equally provide gainful employment of the masses and expand the production base which will, in turn, add value to the community and the Nation at large (Manino, C. 2019).

The NERFUND is not another organization that is raised up to embezzle public funds or distort monies from the government rather, it is important in such a way that it is designed to help in making ordinary Nigerians become extraordinary persons in the field of entrepreneurship. To make this dream a reality, the requirements to giving of funds in NERFUND is strictly based on the efficiency of the benefactor and as you well know that when sugar is poured on the floor, innumerable ants gather, the resources available in NERFUND is quite limited compared to the number of persons applying for the loans, this makes the screening process a bit tough and at the end of the day, only persons who have a good and viable prospect benefit from the program (Manino, C. 2019).

Aside from just the disbursement of loans, other importance of the NERFUND includes:

- Taken up a measure to effect correction upon any inadequacies in providing financing on a long- term basis to small and medium scale enterprises especially when it has to do with manufacturing and agro-allied ancillary services and enterprises.
- It makes provision for loans on a small to long-term basis to commercial and merchant banks that participate in the program for lending to small and medium scale businesses in order to promote and speed up production activities in such companies.
- It ensure and speed up the process of loan disbursement with a lifespan of five to ten years and occasionally, with a grace period of one to three years still dependent upon the nature of the business for which the loan was gotten for.

Benefits of Small and Medium Enterprise

The benefits of Small and medium scale enterprises according to Asikhia & Eze (2010) are seen as follows:

Independence: Entrepreneurs are their own bosses. They make the decisions; they choose whom to do business with and what work they will do. They decide what hours to work, as well as what to pay and whether to take vacations. For many entrepreneurs, the freedom to control their destiny is enough to outweigh the potential risks.

Financial gain: Entrepreneurs offers a greater possibility of achieving significant financial rewards than working for someone else. Owning your own business removes the income restraint that exists in being someone else's employee. Many entrepreneurs are inspired by the mega-millionaire entrepreneurs we see today, such as Steve Jobs, Elon Musk, Jeff Bezos, and Mark Zuckerberg.

Control: it enables one to be involved in the total operation of the business, from concept to design to creation, from sales to business operations to customer response. This ability to be totally immersed in the business is very satisfying to entrepreneurs who are driven by passion and creativity and possess a "vision" of what they aim to achieve. This level of involvement allows the business owner to truly create something of their own.

Prestige: it offers the status of being the person in charge. Some entrepreneurs are attracted to the idea of being the boss. In addition, though there is the prestige and pride of ownership. When someone asks, “who did this?” the entrepreneur can answer, “I did”

Equity: it gives an individual the opportunity to build equity, which can be kept, sold, or passed on to the next generation. It's not uncommon for entrepreneurs to own multiple businesses throughout their life. They establish a company, run it for a while, and later sell it to someone else. The income from this sale can then be used to finance the next venture. If they are not interested in selling the business, the goal may be to build something that can be passed down to their children to help ensure their financial benefits of a business venture, you need to be the owner.

Opportunity: entrepreneurship creates an opportunity for a person to make a contribution. Most new entrepreneurs help the local economy. A few through their innovations, contribute to society as a whole.

In addition, small businesses have certain benefits over large businesses. Flexibility, generally lean staffing, and the ability to develop close relationships with customers are among the key benefits of small businesses. The digital communication revolution has significantly lowered the cost of reaching customers, and this has been a boon to small startups and big businesses alike.

Causes of Small and Medium Scale enterprises Failure

Small and medium scale enterprises are faced with variety of problems. According to Obikoya (2014); management of small and medium scale industries frequently find trouble in the following areas; competition which usually could result into waste of resources in an enterprising. It is a known fact that many small and medium scale enterprises fail in their early stage of development for pressures experienced from the bigger companies lack of capital (which unless empowerment comes from agencies and government) serves a serious hindrance to development and growth of small and medium scale businesses. Occasionally misuse of capital meant for business into personal events affects or result into failure.

Inaccessible locations of businesses to a greater extent have affected their continuous existence. Infact many small and medium scale industries have collapsed following wrong site for their businesses.

Related to this are premature expansions usually embarked upon by small and medium scale enterprises. This is often prompted by desire to dominate rather than to achieve.

On a general assessment of failure of small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria. ‘ Uzoma (2016:29) attributes it to the following; inadequate sales, heavy operating costs, inventory difficulties, excessive fixed costs, high incidence of bad debts, payment of dividends whether earned or not, ignorance concerning the market, ignorance in the benefits of good recording, and difficulty in providing for management succession.

The above listed factors are recently checkmated by government policies that regulates on one-hand empowering on the other to boast small and medium scale enterprises. According to Olusoya (2016:6), leasing (which could be finance or equipment) have been used by government and her agencies to correcting some factors that leads to small and medium scale enterprises.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study recognized that one major feature of investment in developing countries of sub-saharan Africa (SSA) is the high import content of capital goods. This buttresses the contention in the two gap model (Chenry and Eze, 2012 and Bacha, 2009), that the lack of foreign exchange may constitute a major constraint to sustain high rates of investment and growth in developing economies. Therefore, in countries like Nigeria where both private and public sectors are highly complementary, the lack of government in economic activities will always constitute an impediment to growth.

In other word, government intervention is a crucial determinant factor in the growth of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. This is a serious issue when viewed from the perspective of this study. Therefore, this study is hinged on the following theories, namely: Lewis-Fei-Ranis theory, trickledown theory, theory of proportionate growth and Need for achievement theory.

Lewis-Fei-Ranis Theory

This is an economic model of unemployment in underdeveloped countries, which was made known by Lewis; Fei and Ranis. According to this theory, excess labor supply in the non-profit oriented traditional sector, which cannot be engaged by public and large private enterprises led to the rise and development of SMEs. These efforts symbolized economic reality as they involved human capital. Consistent with this theory, SMEs' growth and development are as a result of the high rate of unemployment and for which SMEs serve as a refuge for the unemployed. In the circumstances of economic crises, such as slow growth or contraction of labor absorption, the SME sector is anticipated to grow in order to serve as an alternative. Conversely, SMEs are at the same time expected to expand when formal employment grows (Willis, 2008).

Trickle down Theory

The Trickledown Theory propounded by Anderson, opined that laying much emphases on the growth in the short run will substantially promote equality in the long run. Six propositions are depicted by the theory which are linked in chronological order, these includes:

1. Business can be encouraged so long as there is a direct profits to entrepreneurs or investors;
2. Such encouragement will hearten the growth of the enterprise;
3. The profits realized from the growth will be invested or reinvested;
4. New jobs will be created from the investment;
5. The jobs will assist in satisfying the total needs of poor persons employed;
6. Through earnings, savings and fresh opportunities in an open society including vocational training, education etc., consequently inequality may be reduce eventually.

In line with this theory, the growth realized at first benefits only the high income groups which later descendent to lower income groups after sometimes. The wealth created by entrepreneur as well trickle down to other poor family members and the society through wealth distribution.

Theory of Proportionate Growth

The second theory related to SMEs and poverty reduction is a popular standard model of firm growth known as the Gibrat's Law of Proportionate, the theory postulates as follows: that there exist no relationship between the size of the firm and its growth rate and that enterprise growth rate are to some extent independent of firm size; each firm (large and small) faces some unexpected shocks; the growth of firm (large and small) depends on their management of shocks.

SMEs being small and flexible can easily resist any kind of distress that want to weigh the business down as compared to large firms. Each shocks experience by small firms could signify injection of new ideas or innovation which makes the firm to remain in business and even stronger (Mbizi, Hove, Thondhlana, & Kakava, 2013), in general, the more the shocks, the higher the growth of SMEs and the less the poverty level (Parker, 2009).

Need for Achievement Theory

Another theory is that of Need for Achievement Theory of McClelland. Need for achievement theory is a motivational based theory which focuses primarily on goal-directed behavior of need of achievement rather than multiple needs. The theory laid emphasis on individual and society and that societal level of needs for achievement varies which explain differences in economic growth. Therefore, the ultimate way to promote economic development in poor countries is to raise higher the levels of needs of achievement among indigenous populations. Based on this model, recent evidence abound that there exist a positive relationship between need of achievement and entrepreneurship activity. Entrepreneurship with high need of achievement will involves greater SMEs activities which will create wealth, then, this wealth will fosters poverty alleviation (Jex & Brith, 2014).

The Theory Underpinning the study

Based on the theories of SMEs and poverty explained in the preceding section, the trickledown theory was found to capture the relationship between the four components of SMEs (employment, innovation, human capital development and income) and poverty reduction, and thereby been adopted for the study. Established on the premises of the theory, innovative activities of the business provide direct profit (income) to the entrepreneurs or investors; the profit realized from the growth of the business will be invested and re-invested, and new jobs (employment) will be created from the investment; the earnings from the jobs will help to meet the needs of the poor (persons in poverty) employed; and through earnings, savings may be realized which can open opportunity for further training or education (human capital development), and consequently reduces inequality eventually.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Development of Small and Medium Enterprises

To facilitate the growth and development of small scale enterprise in a country or in a region, it is necessary to identify those creative branches that have a potential for growth, their location in the country or region, and to quantify their potential for inducing socio-economic growth.

The environment in which SMEs in Europe, South East Asia and America operate provides stable power and water supply, standard road and rail network, efficient water and air transport system, advanced technology, modern communication facilities, efficient and responsive financial system, and above all good governance. Unless Nigeria puts its policies right, many SMEs may not survive this competitive drive. It is our hope that the following elements will assist in creating an enabling environment for development, competitiveness and growth of SMEs in Nigeria:

Financing Small and Medium Enterprises

Creative businesses can sometimes access funds/benefits from such sources as personal investments, grants for promoting creativity, for business start-up, private R&D spending, tax deductions, loans and philanthropy, amongst others. However, as may be expected the lack of financing is impeding the growth of the sector, even in developed economies. The capital required for the development and implementation of promising ideas is frequently lacking.

Fiscal Incentives and Support

Tax rebate - for SMEs that put effort on local sourcing of raw materials, serious in adding value to commodities for exports and other business ethics, which government may wish to foster. Similarly, government could increase funding for the development of the sub-sector through direct budgetary allocations and enhance private sector investment opportunities that will focus on specific areas of capacity enhancement.

Infrastructure Development

Develop and upgrade rural/urban road and rail network, water and air transport system, and communication infrastructure by Government and the private sector.

Cluster Formation

Encourage networking among SMEs operators and use of shared facilities such as Common Facility Centre (CFC).

This also involves development of and access to information and communication technology, and partnership among operators, which will help reduce cost of production and improve product quality and competitiveness. In this way, the SMEs would be positioning themselves to benefit from the implementation of the proposed programme of NEPAD (Joron, Fosco & Keljin, 2015)

Concept of Industrialization

Most of the empirical and theoretical arguments in favour of the concept of industrialization have been summarized by Bolaky (2011). Historically, it represents a transition from an economy based on agriculture to one in which manufacturing represents the principal means of subsistence. Consequently, two dimensions of industrialization are the work that people do for a living (economic activity) and the actual goods they produce (economic output). Other dimensions include the manner in which economic activity is organized (organization). The energy or power source used (mechanization) and the systematic methods and innovative practices employed to accomplish work (technology).

Industrialization has two distinct meanings: it can be conceived as a shift in a country's pattern of output and work force towards manufacturing or secondary industry (Clunies-Ross, Foresyth, & Huq, 2010). It can also be defined in terms of income levels reaching a certain threshold.

O'Sullivan and Sheffrin (2007) defined industrialization as the process of societal and economic change that transforms a human from agrarian to an industrial one. In their view, industries bring about change in three ways: modernization, the development of large scale energy and metallurgy production. These aspects are closely linked to economic growth. They also assert that industrialization brings with it the sociological process of rationalization. Overtime, various strategies have been used to promote industrial growth. These are balanced growth, unbalanced growth, import substitution and export promotion.

3. METHODOLOGY

Under the research methodology, the researcher intends to finding out the impact of government funding on the promotion and development of small and medium scale enterprise in Jos South local government area of Plateau State.

Due to the above assertion, the researcher list the method that will be used to carry out the research, these methods are population of the study, sample size, research questions, source of data collection, methods of data collection and method of data analysis.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Eguzoikpe (2008) defined population as the collection of all possible observation of specified characteristic of interest. From the above definition, the researcher can say that a population is the collection of the element under study and the researcher is trying to draw conclusion.

This refers to the number from which a sample is drawn. The population size for this work shall be 100 SMEs within Jos South Local Government Area.

SAMPLE SIZE

Eguzoikpe (2008), defined sampling as the mechanism of choosing designated quantities or proportion as representations of whole population. Sample as a portion, or part or a subset of the population of intersects.

The formula used in calculating the sample size is Taro Yamane formula. Thus, the formula is presented below;

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + N(e)^2)}$$

Where;

n = Sample Size

N = Number of People in the Population

e = allowable error (%)

$n = \frac{100}{(1+100(0.10)^2)}$

$n = \frac{100}{(1+100(0.01)^2)}$

$n = \frac{100}{(1+1)}$

$n = \frac{100}{2}$

$n = 50$

Therefore, the sample size of the study shall be 50 SMEs within Jos South LGA to represent the total population.

SOURCE OF DATA COLLECTION

The questionnaire was the instrument used to elicit data from the respondents. The instrument was designed in an analytical form only.

Primary Data

Okpanachi (2012) defined primary data as the data obtained from the original source by the researcher. It may be obtained from representatives, individuals or organization through questionnaire, observation and interview method.

Secondary Data

Okpanachi (2012) defined secondary data as the data collected by someone other than the user. It is all the information collected for the purpose other than the completion of a research project and is used to gain initial insight into the research problem.

The instrument for data collection in the study was a structured questionnaire, which were designed through the research literature review.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Simple random sampling was used during the data collection that cut across the areas where small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are predominantly located in the local government area. Two instruments of data collection were used: the questionnaire and interviews.

However, while the questionnaire was the major instrument, the interview complemented it.

The questionnaires was used to extract information from the small and medium enterprises operators who are responsible for the running of the day to day administration of the enterprises in the study area in order to have relevant on the impact of government interventions on the growth of small scale enterprises in the area. Data collected from the issuance of questionnaire and interviews were presented (in figure using percentage)

METHOD OF DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Analysis refers to the screening through with the purpose to ascertain desired results. For the purpose of this study, one important statistical tool is use to be employed in analyzing the fact (data gathered which include):

- **Simple Percentage Method:** This method will be use to analyze most of the questionnaire. All responses analyzed where presented in percentage.

Using the simple percentage method of data analyzed. Below is the formula for simple percentage:

$$\text{Simple percentage (\%)} = \frac{NR}{TQ} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where; NR = Number of Respondents
TQ = Total Questionnaires.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

This chapter is very vital to the whole research work, this is simply because it will be concerned with the data presentation and analysis of data collected from the field which on its own will not give any meaningful information unless they are been manipulated and classified in tabular form. It is through these means that one can give meaning to the raw data that generate the required information for usage.

The response will be presented from the questionnaire administered one after another in a tabular form before analyzing the analytical techniques employed by this research work.

Data Presentation

The researcher distributed fifty (50) questionnaires to business owners in Jos South Metropolis. And all the fifty (50) questionnaires were collected by the researcher and they were good for analytical purpose.

Table 1: Number of questionnaires distributed

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Returned questionnaire	50	100
Not returned questionnaires	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above out of fifty (50) questionnaires that were distributed to business owners in Jos South. Fifty were returned. Therefore analysis will be based on the returned questionnaires.

Table 2: Accessing the Intervention fund required legal mortgage whereby so many SMEs in Jos South L.G.A do not have the requirement to the loan

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	25	50
Agree	10	20
Undecided	5	10
Disagreed	10	20
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 25 respondents representing 50 % strongly agree that accessing the intervention fund required legal mortgage whereby so many SMEs in Jos South do not have the requirement to the loan, 10 respondents representing 20% agree to that, 5 respondents representing 10 % are undecided, while 10 respondents representing 20% Disagreed to that fact. Thus this implies that accessing the intervention fund require legal mortgage whereby so many SMEs in Jos South do not have the requirement to the loan.

Table 3: Question: There is also condition on debenture on asset of SMEs before accessing the intervention fund

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	22	44
Agree	10	20
Undecided	18	36
Disagreed	-	-
Strongly Disagreed	-	-

Total**50****100****Source: Field Survey 2022**

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 22 respondents representing 44% strongly agree that there is also condition on debenture on asset of SMEs before accessing the intervention fund, 10 respondent representing 20% agree to that, while 18 respondent representing 36% are undecided. Thus this implies that there is also condition on debenture on asset of SMEs before accessing the intervention fund.

Table 4: There is Internal Bank guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtained the loan

Response	No. of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	25	50
Agree	10	20
Undecided	15	30
Disagreed	-	-
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 25 respondents representing 50% strongly agree that there is internal bank guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtain loan, 10 respondents representing 20% agree to that, 15 respondents representing 30% are undecided. thus this implies that there are internal bank guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtain loan.

Table 5: There is also external guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtained the loan

Response	No. of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	35	70
Agree	15	30
Undecided	-	-
Disagreed	-	-
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 35 respondents representing 70% strongly agree that there is also external guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtained the loan, while 15 respondents representing 30% agree to that. Thus, this implies that there is also external guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtained loan.

Table 6: There is effective innovative output among SMES in Jos South L.G.A

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	30	60
Agree	13	26
Undecided	7	14
Disagreed	-	-
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 30 respondents representing 60% strongly agree that there is effective innovative output among SMEs, 13 respondents representing 26 % agree to that, while 7

respondents representing 14% are undecided. Thus this implies that there is effective innovative output among SMEs in Jos South L.G.A

Table 7: Question: There is effective research and development output among SMEs owners in Jos South L.G.A

Response	No. of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	30	60
Agree	20	40
Undecided	-	-
Disagreed	-	-
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 30 respondents representing 60% strongly agree that there is effective research and development output among SMEs owners, while 20 respondents representing 40% agree to that. Thus this implies that there is effective research and development output among SMEs owners.

Table 8: There is efficient and effective production output among SMEs owners in Jos South L.G.A

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	40	80
Agree	8	16
Undecided	2	4
Disagreed	-	-
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 40 respondent representing 80% strongly agree that there is efficient and effective production output among SMEs owners, 8 respondents representing 16% agree to that, while 2 respondent representing 4% are undecided. Thus this implies that there is efficient and effective production output among SMEs owners.

Table 9: Question: There is effective technological development or improvement among SMES in Jos South L.G.A

Response	No. of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	30	60
Agree	5	10
Undecided	10	20
Disagreed	5	10
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 30 respondents representing 60% strongly agree that there is effective technological development among SMEs, 5 respondents representing 10% agree to that, 10 respondents representing 20% are undecided while 5 respondents representing 10% Disagreed to that. Thus this implies that there is effective technological development among SMEs.

Table 10: SMEs in Jos South L.G.A offered most people part-time employment

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	15	30
Agree	15	30
Undecided	5	10
Disagreed	10	20
Strongly Disagreed	5	10
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 15 respondents representing 30% strongly agree that SMEs in Jos South L.G.A offered most people part-time employment, 15 respondents representing 30% agree to that, 5 respondents representing 10% are undecided, 10 respondents representing 20% Disagreed to that, while 5 respondents, representing 10% strongly Disagreed. Thus this implies that SMEs in Jos South L.G.A offered most people part-time employment.

Table 11: Majority of people are self-employed due to SMEs growth in Jos South L.G.A

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	20	40
Agree	15	30
Undecided	10	20
Disagreed	5	10
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 20 respondents representing 40% strongly agreed that majority of people are self-employed due to SMEs in Jos South L.G.A, 15 respondents representing 30% agreed to that, 10 respondents representing 20% are undecided while 5 respondents, representing 10% Disagreed to that. Thus this implies that majority of people are self-employed due to SMEs.

Table 12: Majority of the people received payment from being employed by SMEs in Jos South L.G.A

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	25	50
Agree	15	30
Undecided	5	10
Disagreed	5	10
Strongly Disagreed	-	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 25 respondents representing 50% choose strongly agreed, 15 respondents, representing 30% agreed to the fact, 5 respondents representing 10% are undecided and 5 respondents representing 10% Disagreed to the fact. Thus this implies that majority of the people received payment from being employed by SMEs.

Table 13: There is frequent contract employment in Jos South L.G.A among SMEs

Options	No. of Questionnaires	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed	37	74
Agree	13	26
Undecided	0	-
Disagreed	0	-
Strongly Disagreed	0	-
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

From the table above, it was understood that a total number of 37 respondents representing 74% choose Strongly Agreed, while 13 respondents, representing 26% Agree to the fact. Thus this implies that there is frequent contract employment in Jos South L.G.A among SMEs.

Result of Findings

Accessing intervention fund requires legal mortgage whereby so many SMEs in Jos South do not have the requirement to loan. The stringent procedures and requirements for getting loan has made it practically impossible for SMEs to get loan to boost their businesses.

There is internal bank guarantor which is very difficult for SMEs to obtain loan. Most SMEs in Jos South are faced with low capital base and so getting a guarantor has become very difficult.

The need external guarantor has made it difficult for SMEs to obtain loan. Getting a surety especially on financial issues is very difficult due to perceived uncertainty of business progress.

There is effective innovative output among SMEs in Jos South LGA. An innovative entrepreneur has a great chance of success because of the injection of new ideas and inventions into the business place.

There is effective research and development output among SMEs owners. An entrepreneur who engages in business research shall always have good output because his decision will always be timely.

There is effective technological development or improvement among SMEs in Jos South. The advent of technology has effectively changed the course of doing business as it has improve production and productivity.

Small and Medium enterprises in Jos South have provided jobs for several people. The offshoot of businesses has become a major source of employment. It has made many to be self employed.

5. Findings

In the preview chapter, the researcher presented and analyzed data. This chapter is essentially articulate it discusses the main kernels of the research findings and proffers pertinent recommendations.

Summary of findings

National economic resource fund has funded several businesses in the country and it is meant to develop small and medium enterprise for several and growth. The research looks at access to finance or funding industrialization and financial excises in developing variable for developing SMES.

Access to capital is a major issue that can guarantee the success of a business and so straight out process in acquiring loan by small and medium enterprise has hamper its group and survival .Most of the SMES the financial base to win the confidence and trust of someone to serve as guarantor in for them to access some loans or funding from financial institution. The uncertain nature of SMEs in terms of growth and buoyancy has made it difficult for people to stand as sureties in accessing loan.

Innovation is what can change the fortunes of any business. Entrepreneurs who engage in innovation has great chance of success in growth and development as innovation is all about injecting new ideas and intentions into the business. Effective research carried out by an entrepreneur could always born good outputs as the decisions of the business are always base on comment realities.

Technology has come to stay as its advent has come to change the course of doing business. It has improved production and productivity thereby increasing business output. The engagement of people in small and medium enterprise has made them self-employed and has also provided employment opportunities to several others either directly or indirectly.

Conclusion

This project work examine the role of NERFUND in promoting small and medium scale enterprise in Jos south Local government Metropolis, the study revealed that NERFUND have Impact on small and medium scale enterprises.

Recommendations

In view of the foregoing review the following recommendations are suggested for improvement of the role of government in promoting of small scales in Nigeria.

- i. In order to reduce the risk in small scales lending, the Central bank of Nigeria and the government can do more than they are currently doing be boarding the credit guarantee scheme. Rediscounting by the state government can sample possibilities for encouraging local government to gain experience in medium and long-term lending operation. A number of procedures can be adopted such as preferential discount rates multiple discount rate or quotes favouring certain purpose.
- ii. In order to make credit available to small scales industrial sector, the government and the public should more use of the rural banking programme. The branches of each bank in the rural communities should be given free hand to take certain decision concerning advancement of these loans and advances to rural small scales industrials they should be able to act as management consultants identifying problems and suggesting solutions.
- iii. The government should combine savings scheme for small scales industrial sector with their credit programme such as a scheme would provided further means of financing the government and create attachment of the industrialist to the government and also solve the problem of very short moratorium period granted government to small scales which has provide inadequate for the funding of industrial activity in which the borrowers are engaged in there by carting repayment programme problem.
- iv. The Federal government has established an insurance scheme to protect the hazard interest in industrial production; this should also extend to the small scales industrial sector. This policy should be implanted immediately without further delay. It will encourage local government to lend medium and long term funds. It will also enable to grant a longer period of moratorium on loans for the small scales.

Suggestion for Further Studies

The following are the suggestions for further studies the researcher suggest;

- i. The Effects of social media on the sales promotion of small and medium scale enterprises.
- ii. The impact of central bank on Small and medium scale enterprises
- iii. The effects of cashless economy system on small and medium scale enterprises

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